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SELECTIVE ENCRYPTION OF IMAGE BY NUMBER MAZE TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Due to enormous increase in the usage of computers and mobiles, today's world is currently flooded with huge volumes of data. This paper is primarily focused on multimedia data and how it can be protected from unwanted attacks. Sharing of multimedia data is easy and very efficient, it has been a customary practice to share multimedia data but there is no proper encryption technique to encrypt multimedia data. Sharing of multimedia data over unprotected networks using DCT algorithm and then applying selective encryption-based algorithm has never been adequately studied. This paper introduces a new selective encryption-based security system which will transfer data with protection even in unauthenticated network. Selective encryption-based security system will also minimize time during encryption process which there by achieves efficiency. The data in the image is transmitted over a network is discriminated using DCT transform and then it will be selectively encrypted using Number Puzzle technique, and thus provides security from unauthorized access. This paper discusses about numeric puzzle-based encryption technique and how it can achieve security and integrity for multimedia data over traditional encryption technique.

KEYWORDS

multimedia security, selective encryption; DCT compression; cipher image

For More Details: <https://wireilla.com/ijcis/abstract/10220ijcis01.html>

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TOWARDS A DEEPER NTRU ANALYSIS: A MULTI MODAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

NTRU is being considered as part of the NIST quantum resistant cryptography standard. While NIST has received substantial attention in the literature, more analysis is needed. This current study uses a unique approach. The team of researchers divided into -sub-teams. Each is using a separate analysis technique on NTRU. Then the diverse -sub-teams' work was brought together into a single cohesive statistical analysis to provide well-founded conclusions regarding NTRU.

KEYWORDS

NTRU, NTRU Encrypt, Post Quantum Cryptography, Quantum Resistant Cryptography

For More Details: <https://wireilla.com/ijcis/abstract/10220ijcis02.html>

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